

1 **The ERBB family functions in lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
8 ERBB2, ERBB3 and ERBB4 as lineage commitment cooperating factors in embryonic stem cells of the
9 human embryo. Fate choice proceeding through EGFR/HER2-4 pathway signals reinforced lineage
10 commitment signals.

11 Citations

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